

Opportunities for Business Innovation and Service Delivery for Policy

Project Identification	
Project Full Title	Water scenarios for Copernicus Exploitation
Project Acronym	Water-ForCE
Grant Agreement	101004186
Starting date	01.01.2021
Duration	36 months

Document Identification	
Deliverable number	D6.3
Deliverable Title	Opportunities for Business Innovation and Service Delivery for Policy
Type of Deliverable	Report
Dissemination Level	Public (PU)
Work Package	WP6
Leading Partner	USTIR

History of Changes

Date	Version	Comments
22/03/2023	V0	Working draft sent around Water-ForCE group for review
21/04/2023	V1	First draft sent out for internal review
3/05/2023	V2	Review from full general assembly
11/07/2023	v3	Updated with comments from Advisory Board and external advisors. - Final version.

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	7
1.1 Water-ForCE	7
1.2 Definitions used in this report	8
1.3 Scope of the report	8
2. Sources of information used in this report	10
3. The Copernicus Programme within the Inland Water Value Chain	12
3.1 Copernicus and the EO data and Services Market	12
3.2 The Inland Water Value Chain	14
3.3 The roles of the Copernicus Programme within industry and end-user sectors	16
3.4 Defining opportunities for business innovation and service delivery	20
4. Drivers and challenges for the Inland Water sector	22
5. Opportunities within the Inland Water Value Chain	25
5.1 Infrastructure providers (back-end)	25
5.2 Data providers	27
5.3 Platform providers (front-end)	27
5.4 EO products and service providers	29
5.6 Information providers	30
6. Opportunities driven by end-user needs	31
6.1 Agriculture	33
6.2 Drinking water, utilities, water allocation & urban water management	35
6.3. Energy (Oil & Gas, Renewable Energies)	38
6.4. Environmental accounting, assurance compliance, and ESG's	40
6.5. Health	42
6.6. Insurance for Natural Disasters	44
6.7. Indigenous-led water management	46
6.8. Mining & Raw materials	49
6.9. Transport	50
7. Strategy for Copernicus Programme business opportunities	52

8.1 Key actions for the Copernicus Programme	52
References	54

Executive summary

As the biggest EO data provider in the world, Copernicus Programme plays a huge role in the EO market. In addition to being a data and infrastructure provider, the Copernicus Programme, and related funding bodies (e.g., EUSPA, European Space Agency), also have influence within the commercial sector through various other mechanisms (e.g., sector-based funding strategies, research funding, coordination and capacity building). The water sector is an enormous industry sector, with huge realised and potential opportunities for use of EO and Copernicus products and services. Unfortunately, an immediate impediment to understanding these opportunities is the lack of information on the sector, which is typically represented within other market segments such as agriculture. The first attempts at defining the inland water value chain were presented in D1.5 and are used within this deliverable. For each step in the value chain, the opportunities are assessed and the potential role of Copernicus in supporting the sector. It is likely that downstream EO data and service providers are the largest revenue, who benefit from consistent and free-to-access data provisions by the Copernicus Core Services, however their needs must be balanced with supporting and promoting competitiveness among the EU space industry (i.e., through commercial products). The key end-users (i.e., customers for the water sector) were then analysed to identify possible actions of the Copernicus programme in realising emerging opportunities. Small changes in uptake of EO data within large sectors such as Insurance and Energy, could result in large Copernicus enabled revenues. Commercial EO applications which promote EU policy goals (e.g., Environmental monitoring for improved ecosystem management) will likely benefit from support through explicit reference of EO within policy to increase trust, and direct funding. The lack of skilled personnel and lack of trust in EO data are currently holding the sector back, and can be addressed through capacity building and a commitment to improving cal/val and a dedicated in situ component. A full list of priority actions are outlined at the end of the report.

Disclaimer

The Information, documentation and figures available in this deliverable are written by the Water-ForCE Consortium members and do not necessarily reflect the view of the EC.

This document is partly based on the EC's official documents however, no legal responsibility can be taken for the contents in this document. Any doubt regarding administration and reporting should be solved by consulting the official documents or through the Coordination Team, who will consult for an official EC response, if necessary.

1. Introduction

1.1 Water-ForCE

The Horizon-2020 project Water-ForCE (Water scenarios For Copernicus Exploitation) will develop a Roadmap for Copernicus Inland Water Services.

The Roadmap will contain:

- Analysis of user communities' landscape
- Analysis on how Copernicus water-related services can support policy development and monitoring of their implementation
- Gap analysis of the Copernicus water-related service portfolio
- Identification of future potential higher-level biogeochemical products
- Technical requirements for future Copernicus sensors to improve the water-related service portfolio
- Proposal for organising in-situ measurement networks to validate Copernicus remote sensing and modelling products and to provide complementary data not collected by remote sensing
- Proposal on how to define relationships between Core Services and Downstream services
- Scenarios of the most optimal delivery of water services to different user communities.

The Water-ForCE project is coordinated by the University of Tartu (Estonia) with 20 participating organisations from all over Europe. It connects experts in water quality and quantity, in policy, research, engineering and service sectors.

1.2 Definitions used in this report

Sector: A general term to categorise a group of industries and markets which share common attributes (i.e., they all deal with inland water data). Inland water is a sector we discuss within this group.

Industry: A specific group of similar types of companies.

Value chain: The process or activities by which a sector (i.e., the inland water sector) adds value to EO data.

Market: A group of customers.

Segment / Segmentation: Different groups within a market.

End-user: End-users are the final users or benefactors of inland water EO data. Paying end-users are customers. End-users in this report are grouped by their sector, i.e., other sectors which are customers for the inland water EO- related products.

1.3 Scope of the report

The gap analysis undertaken in T6.2 will be used in the Task 6.3 to highlight the downstream business innovation opportunities in service of technologies that are better delivered by research and business communities that deliver bespoke services tuned to the needs of individual organisations, sectors and national agencies and therefore fall outside the scope of the Copernicus Land Service. Such opportunities provide the platform for business development stimulating economic growth and societal benefit. This task will work closely with all sectors to assess the landscape for development and make recommendations for future funding calls that facilitate the

co-development of these opportunities in either the short- or longer-term. The objectives of this report are as follows:

1. to summarise the business and innovation opportunities made in the deliverables from WP1-5 (and maybe some additional sources),
2. to summarise and assess the recommendations made in the deliverables from WP1-5,
3. to propose future actions and objectives for the improved impact of Copernicus within the inland and coastal water domain,
4. to assess the ability of existing programmes and projects to meet the proposed objectives,
5. to advise on the maintenance of monitoring, and evaluation of proposed objectives.

2. Sources of information used in this report

There are numerous sources of information used in this report (Figure 4). Firstly, within the Water-ForCE project there are a number of private companies within the EU industry that are able to provide insight ([DotSpace](#), [Synergise](#), [Antea](#), [Vito](#), [3edata](#), [Water Insight](#), [isardSAT](#)). There are also a number of deliverables disseminating the market and providing a foundation for this report, including **D1.4** “Report on end-user needs and requirements’ ’, and **D1.5** “Innovation needs and opportunities”. Deliverable D1.5 includes extensive interviews with a further 6 stakeholders and companies.

Figure 4. Summary of the sources of information used in this report.

Secondly, opportunities for business sectors have been distilled from all work packages within the Water-ForCE consortium. These include the WP2 Water Quality community, WP3 Water quantity community, WP4 In situ community and the WP5 Modelling community. Reference to the relevant deliverable or working group will be made throughout. All working groups have formed working groups of experts and have organised workshops and surveys (see **D1.1**, **D1.2**, **D3.1**, **D5.2**, and **D6.1**).

Finally, this report uses information from a vast number of external sources. In particular, the European Association of Remote Sensing companies (EARSC) survey which is completed by EO companies each year. In this report we used information from the [2020](#), [2021](#) and [2022](#) surveys. The EARSC also represents the Industry Position Paper to Copernicus in [2019](#), and [2022](#) representing the EO downstream services industry. Market reports were reviewed from PwC for [2016](#) and [2019](#), as well as the interim report from PwC in [2017](#) and the Copernicus ex-ante benefits assessment in [2017](#). Market report from EUSPA for [2022](#), and the GNSS Market report [2015](#). European Parliament report on Space market uptake within Europe [2016](#).

3. The Copernicus Programme within the Inland Water Value Chain

3.1 Copernicus and the EO data and Services Market

The global market for Earth Observation data and value-added services is an exciting and burgeoning market. In 2021 the market turnover was €2.8 bn and is predicted to grow to €5.5 bn by 2031 (EUSPA, 2022). Despite the global pandemic, the EARSC survey 2022 noted a growth rate of 7.5% since 2018. The majority of revenue, (79% according to EUSPA, 2022), has been in EO value-added services. Revenues from the Inland water domain, the focus of Water-ForCE and this report, are split across some of the largest segments, including Urban development, Agriculture, Climate Services, Energy and Raw Materials and Infrastructure, which together comprise 55% of the market. Optimism Index ratings from companies in the EARS surveys in 2021 and 2022 show higher optimism levels for revenues but consistent concern over employment.

Box 1: *The Space industry At a Glance (see D1.2 for more information)*

Growth: 7.5% growth rate over 5 years but a decline since 2021 (EARSC, 2022)

VAS dominated: Majority of the market share is held by Value-added Services (PwC, 2020 & EARSC, 2021)

Skills needed: Optimism index in 2021 and 2022 showed higher rates for revenues than employment, while the 2022 report showed that the vast majority of the companies had either slight, significant or impossibility of filling positions (EARSC, 2021, 2022)

Small companies: Majority of the sector can be defined as micro or small (EARSC, 2022)

Europe & North America dominated the market: Europe and the USA stand out in terms of their share of the market. Together they comprise 83% of the global market in 2019 and Africa, Middle East, South America, Central America and Australasia do not even get a mention. Europe (EU27 plus Norway, Switzerland and the UK), stands out, however, when it comes to data analysis and Europe has around half of the global market share in Analysis, Insights and Support market in 2019 (EUSPA, 2022).

Revenue generation in the EO industry by key domains (% split of revenues 2019)			
Europe	41%	Canada	4%
US	42%	Japan	3%
China	6%	Others	4%

Figure 1. Revenue generated in the EO industry by relevant domains in 2019 (EUSPA, 2022).

North America & Asia dominate the customer base: The greatest demand, demonstrated through purchase of EO data and value-added services, is found in North America, followed by Asia-Pacific (EUSPA, 2022).

The Copernicus Programme plays a huge role in the EO data provider industry, as the biggest EO data provider in the world, and the third largest data provider in the world (Copernicus, [2022](#)). The Copernicus Program is a global leader in Earth Observation and is regarded by the European EO data and service industry to be the most advanced EO system in the world (Industry Position Paper, 2022). Current figures demonstrate the economic value of the Copernicus Programme to be between €16.2-21.3 bn between 2008 and 2020 (PwC, 2019). This is surplus of €8.0-13.1 bn after accounting for the €8.2 invested into the Programme. The vast majority of this revenue has been generated by end-users. Most companies in the 2021 EARSC survey thought that they will experience a slight increase (37%) or significant increase (44%) in the impact of Copernicus on their business over the coming years. Additionally, the commercial activity resulting from the Copernicus Programme has supported 17,260 jobs years in Europe (PwC, 2019). Economic valuations of the

Copernicus Programme could also include the savings resulting from the insurance sector in particular (see Section 6.4).

Box 2: The value of the Copernicus Programme

💰 Estimated between 4.7 - 9.8 billion euros between 2008 & 2020

🌐 Estimate between 17,260 jobs years between 2008 & 2020

👉 Reliance on Copernicus by EO industry is predicted to increase over the next few years (EARSC, 2021)

(Source: PwC Market Report 2020 & EARSC 2021 survey)

3.2 The Inland Water Value Chain

The representation of the Inland Water sector within market analysis has been a large barrier to understanding the size and the turnover of the sector, and moreover, the opportunities existing within this important sector. Typically inland water applications are distributed across other market segments including agriculture, environmental ecosystems & pollution, fisheries and aquaculture, and utilities & supplies. This limits the ability to determine the size of the market, the coordination and fragmentation of the market and to identify gaps and potential opportunities. To commence the removal of this barrier, Water-ForCE in **D1.5** published a value chain of inland water EO applications. The value chain demonstrates three levels of analysis to present the demand value chain (top), supply value chain (middle) and primary activities value chain (bottom) (Figure 2). EO data providers, can be broken down into infrastructure and data providers, and EO value-added services, can include platform EO product and service providers, and information providers. Of particular use is a list of examples for each step in the value chain, highlighting the public and private offerings. End-users are also listed using the analysis from **D1.4**. A breakdown of the Copernicus-enabled revenue at different stages of the value chain cannot currently be analysed, due to the lack of information, but it is likely that the Inland Water Value chain follows a similar

pattern to the EO market at large, with the majority of revenues accrued by EO value-added services and downstream EO product and service providers (Section 3.1).

Figure 2. Inland water value chain as presented in the **D1.5**, adapted from EUSPA market report in 2022. (see [here](#) for high resolution image)

3.3 The roles of the Copernicus Programme within industry and end-user sectors

The Copernicus Programme has had a huge impact on the EO market and boosted the EU economy since it commenced in 2014 as demonstrated in [Section 3.1](#) (PwC market reports 2015, 2019). Importantly, however, the goal of the Copernicus Programme is not only to deliver products and services through Copernicus Core Services, but also to support both upstream and downstream EO economies within the EU. As explained in the 2022 Industry Position paper represented by EARSC on behalf of downstream EO companies, in order ‘to maximise the maturing power of Europe’s commercial space actors (Large System Integrators, Mid-Caps, SMEs and startups), and foster competitiveness, both in Earth Observation and value-adding services, the Copernicus programme should leverage the variety of existing commercial missions and pertaining complementary EO datasets’ (2022). Building competitiveness in the European EO industry requires that opportunities be made available for the exploitation of the private sector. Careful analysis of each opportunity is necessary to determine whether the benefits are greater if delivered through the Copernicus Core Services or whether the private sector is a more appropriate delivery mechanism (see [D2.4](#)). Thus depending on the strategic approach, the Copernicus Programme plays a diverse number of roles within the market). These roles are discussed below and presented in Figure 2.

Mechanisms to support commercial and non-commercial users

Upstream Downstream

Provide data and infrastructure	Support upstream EO space sector	Support downstream EO providers	Influence EU policy	Offer selective subsidies or cloud space	Set funding agenda	Coordinate communities of practise	Build capacity & awareness
As a data and infrastructure provider, the Copernicus Programme supports commercial and non-commercial users directly.	Copernicus programme can support EO economy by collaborating with third-party groups and by not competing with existing private space companies	Copernicus Programme can support downstream providers by pledging continuity of data/product provisions, and by preventing direct competition with existing downstream providers	Although the Copernicus Programme does not directly write policy, it can promote changes in Policy which will advance the programme.	Copernicus programme do not directly provide grants but may offer subsidised data from the Copernicus contributing missions for research or for specific sectors.	Copernicus programme provide only limited funding directly but can influence the agenda for future funding calls, including research funding, start-up and SME funding.	Copernicus programme and coordinating bodies can facilitate the organisation of different user communities.	Building the necessary awareness of EO and skills among end-user groups towards greater uptake and trust of EO products. This also includes citizen science and social media campaigns (see D6.1)
<i>Sentinel missions and Copernicus Services</i>	<i>E.g., Copernicus contributing missions</i>	<i>E.g., response to EARSC</i>	<i>E.g., call for amendment to WFD to include EO compliance</i>	<i>E.g., commercial data is free for research, cloud-based space for in situ programmes</i>	<i>E.g., Horizon Europe (see greater list in D1.5)</i>	<i>E.g., Copernicus Academy, Coordination projects such as Water-ForCE</i>	<i>E.g., Open competitions such as Copernicus Masters competition</i>

Figure 2. Mechanisms through which the Copernicus Programme (with other coordinating bodies) can support commercial and non-commercial users within the Inland Water sector and the EO market at large. These mechanisms are loosely organised from having an upstream impact (data providers) to a downstream impact (end-user sectors). **For a high-resolution image see [here](#).**

Primarily, the Copernicus Programme is a data provider (see Deliverables **D2.2**, **D3.2** and **D5.2** for review of current Copernicus Products and Services for Inland Water Domain). As a data and infrastructure provider, the Copernicus Programme directly serves many downstream EO services who rely on free access data to continue (EARSC, 2022 Position Paper). Downstream EO data and service providers interact with the Copernicus Programme through various pathways, including through the Copernicus Services which provide value-added products (Figure 3; Pathway 1), or through Copernicus raw data, where downstream EO data/product providers will form their own products (Figure 3; Pathway 2).

Figure 3. Pathways between the Copernicus Programme and downstream EO data and service providers.

Additionally, through Copernicus DIAS (Data and Information Access Services), the Programme enables cloud-based access to data and products with a single access-point, allowing downstream users to host their own applications without having to download bulky files from several access points and process them locally (**D3.2**). In addition to being a direct data and infrastructure provider, the Copernicus Program also collaborates with third-party providers to curate commercial services and products through the Copernicus Contributing Missions (CCM) providing Very High Resolution (VHR) products (see **D2.5**).

In addition to being a data and infrastructure provider, the Copernicus Programme, and related funding bodies (e.g., EUSPA, European Space Agency), also have influence within the private sector through various other mechanisms. Arguably the most important mechanism is to promote certain

policy changes, which sets the EU agenda and determines the regulations within which the private sector must comply (see **D1.3**, **D1.5**, **D3.3**, **D5.4**). Mechanisms can also include providing subsidies and incentives, or public-private partnerships to enable business opportunities which align with EU policy aims. Example of this includes funding start-ups in sustainable technology or offering cloud storage to increase profitability of certain businesses. The Copernicus Programme also has an influence in the agenda for future research and innovation funding opportunities. The Horizon Europe programme has led a number of open calls with specific relevance for Inland water and EO applications (see Section 4.4 in **D1.5**), and in particular a call titled '*Taking EO downstream applications to market*' has enabled a number of water related projects to enter the private sector. EU missions are another mechanism for setting the research and innovation agenda, to match with EU policy aims. The Copernicus Programme can also indirectly drive business and innovation through enabling coordination between communities of practice and building capacity, which indirectly addresses the need for greater awareness and trust in EO among end-user sectors and a greater number of EO-skilled personnel to fill employment needs (see **D6.1**).

3.4 Defining opportunities for business innovation and service delivery

Opportunities are defined as demands within the market that could be filled within the Inland Water Value chain. These opportunities can be taken up by the Copernicus Programme or by the private sector. Opportunities for business and service delivery for policy can be **driven** by changes in the market or policy environment (Figure 4). For example, new digital technology is dramatically transforming big data analysis, such as dealing with EO data, and introducing new cloud-based service models at various stages of the value chain (D1.5). Drivers may also include local or global pressures such as degradation of the EU's water bodies resulting in an increased demand for monitoring applications such as harmful algal warning systems (EEA, [2021](#)). Notably, there are also **challenges** that influence the success of opportunities, such as the resistance of the market to new technologies, lack of skilled personnel for employment, and small customer base.

Opportunities may be evaluated in terms of the **economic and societal impacts** (Figure 4). Economic measures include the revenue of a company and employment rates. Social measures include the risk to human health and addressing of sustainable development goals. Environmental measures include determining the impact on ecosystems, if the opportunity reduces greenhouse emissions etc. The policy environment (Figure 4) describes the policy and decision making mechanisms which are put in place to influence the market in specific ways. Examples include policy which increases the demand for certain markets, such as improving the trust in EO data through explicit reference in legislation (see D5.4 for EU member states EO legislation).

Figure 4. Framework for understanding opportunities within business innovation and services delivery. Business opportunities can be created as a result of challenges and drivers and can be evaluated in terms of their economic and society impacts ([see high resolution image here](#)).

4. Drivers and challenges for the Inland Water sector

Analysis of the emerging user requirements in WaterForce (D1.4), and the drivers of the Inland Water sector (D1.5) points to ample research and business opportunities across the Inland Water Value Chain. Further to this, opportunities specific to certain communities within the Water sector were identified throughout engagement activities (See Section 2). Notably, there are some key drivers of change within the Inland Water sector which are highlighted below. These include changes to the policy environment, digital technology and environmental and climate change pressures. There are also challenges facing the market, which include a lack of trust in EO data, which is closely related to a lack of in situ data, as well as a general lack of skilled personnel.

Box 3. Drivers of opportunities for the Inland Water Value Chain

Digital Transformation

A digital transformation is happening at all of the value chain, particularly since EO data is “big data” (Copernicus, 2023). This includes the increase of cloud-based services models which lower computational and data storage costs and machine learning and AI changing the data analysis processes (see D1.5, D5.3).

European Green Deal & future policy

The Green Deal, presented by the EU in 2019, and future policies addressing issues such as climate mitigation, have the potential to increase the demand for EO services (D1.5, EARSC, 2022). They can do this via increasing support for EO-related industries, including EO as a recognised method for reporting on water regulations and by actually developing policy with EO capabilities in mind. Although explicit reference to Earth Observation methods within EU legislation is lacking

(see D1.2 and D5.4), EO is likely to be included as a recognised methodology within the Water Framework Directive in the next few years ([See recent proposal for a directive amendment, 2022](#)).

Green investment

The shift towards green investment can increase the need for accurate and near-real time monitoring of water resources and environmental conditions. EU Policy goals have also driven green investments including the Sustainable Europe Investment Plan (SEIP) aimed at supporting projects which address the European Green Deal goals (EUSPA, 2022). Impacts are also seen within the private-sector where there has been growth in investment focused on environmental, social and governance (ESG) or ‘greening’ of portfolios. These policy-driven changes in investment can provide investment opportunities for EO applications within the Inland Water sector which clearly meet EU policy goals.

Environmental pressure and climate change

Climate change poses a massive threat to the health of water bodies and catchments worldwide. The need to mitigate against these changes drives many EO-based technologies (EEA, [2021](#)). Additionally, pollution and environmental degradation are also increasing the demand for business innovation within the Inland Water sector.

Sustainable development goals

The sustainable development goals (discussed in detail in D1.6) place water in centre place, with relevance for agriculture, emergency re

Box 3. Challenges for the Inland Water Value Chain

Lack of trust in EO

Surprisingly, Water-ForCE survey results (D6.1 survey) demonstrate strong awareness and confidence in the usefulness of satellite-EO data within the water domain, although other sources find lower confidence (Agnoli et al., 2023). Similarly, a lack of trust in EO data among potential commercial users and customers has been identified as a factor by other organisations (D1.4, Industry Position Paper 2020). A key area of concern is the lack of in situ data and the quality of cal/val data (Agnoli et al., 2023, also see D3.4 Section 6 for Floods). Insufficient or uncoordinated in situ data for cal/val has been identified by various groups within Water-ForCe (D6.1, D2.3, WP4). While primarily this is a challenge for the current EO-based Inland water value chain, it may also offer opportunities to address the gap including data providers and platform providers (D4.3).

Skilled personnel shortages

The space industry has a massive skills gap in general (see D6.1 and EARSC 2021 survey results) and therefore there is a huge employment opportunity to be realised at the individual level, but also with relevance for the EU economy as a whole. The private sector had particularly high needs for capacity development in big data processing (D6.3) (Also see D5.3 for pitfalls of machine-learning and artificial intelligence- including skill needed, complexity of finding the expertise needed for many applications) . Certain activities within the inland water value chain have higher specialised skills demands and are more impacted by a skills shortage. Skills shortages may also be due to skilled personnel being attracted to other employment, for example, more recognised big data applications or where the rewards are higher.

Lack of representation of inland water assets

Overall there is a lack of representation and understanding of the inland and coastal water value chain. This is evident from the lack of inland water as a recognised value chain within the Copernicus market review, but also the exclusion of inland water from ‘green’ and ‘blue’ economies. While coastal issues are somewhat represented in the blue economy, neither economies explicitly incorporate inland waters. This lack of representation may result in unmet needs and opportunities of the inland water value chain and an underestimation of its importance, including economically but also socially and environmentally. Inland water has not yet been incorporated into carbon accounting, nor newer biodiversity accounting.

5. Opportunities within the Inland Water Value Chain

Opportunities and challenges relating to specific activities within the inland water value chain are explored in Table 2. For each primary activity, the EO within the sector at large, identifies gaps within the Copernicus Programme currently and makes some suggestive actions that could be undertaken by the Copernicus Programme to either fill this gap or facilitate the market.

5.1 Infrastructure providers (back-end)

Infrastructure providers deliver computing infrastructure upon which EO can be accessed, stored and processed. Infrastructure providers offer back-end services, while platform providers (Section 5.3) offer front-end computing services, although often the same companies offer both. The key opportunity and driver of change for infrastructure providers is the shift to cloud-based computing and the implementation of Infrastructure as a Service models (IaaS). These include providers such as T-systems, Amazon, Google Cloud, and DIAS (Creodias, Mundi, Sobloo, WekEO and Onda), who host large repositories or offer cluster computing for the Copernicus Programme. Since Copernicus is the third largest data provider in the world, producing over 12 terabytes of data per day (Copernicus, [2018](#)), the storage and organisation of data will continue to evolve with changes in technology. T-systems is currently the infrastructure provider for the new Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem, hosting 34 petabytes, and likely to grow to 80 petabytes over the next few years. There are many opportunities for advancements in technologies that can improve and reduce the cost of data storage, for example Data Cubes (**D2.4**) (see the Euro Data Cube Platform - [Copernicus; https://eurodatacube.com/](#)) and increase the uptake of EO data by simplifying the process (**D5.1, D6.1**). There is also an opportunity that will arise from providing cloud space for downstream or in situ data if there are sufficient benefits of doing so.

Table 2. Opportunities within the Inland Water value chain, established from Water-ForCE deliverables and external documents (*High resolution table can be found [here](#)*)

	Opportunities for the sector at large	Opportunities relate to Copernicus Programme	The potential role of Copernicus
<p>Infrastructure providers</p> <p>Providers of various types of computing infrastructure upon which EO data can be accessed, stored, distributed or manipulated.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cloud service models provide Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) Constant growth in amounts of data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Repository curation & storage of in situ data leading to higher quality data & harmonised datasets (D4.3) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investment in in situ harmonisation projects including funding call opportunities (D4.3)
<p>Data providers</p> <p>Providers of unprocessed or pre-processed EO data.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cloud service models to provide data as a Service (DaaS) Opportunity within the Copernicus Contributing Missions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The development of in situ data networks or cal/val sites (D4.2) Development & innovation for in situ sensors (D4.2, D4.4, D6.2) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investment in smart sensor technology, drones, IoT devices to support water sector (WP1, D4.4)
<p>Platform providers</p> <p>Providers of online platforms and/or digital services, through which users can utilise tools and capabilities to analyse EO data, develop algorithms and build applications.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cloud service models to provide Platform as a Service (Paas) Demand to understand and curate data from end-users, through user-platforms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Platforms to meet specific end-user needs including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water Framework Directive reporting SDG reporting (D1.6) Large benefits in improving the 'ease' of data access (EARSC, 2022, D5.2) Demand from downstream users for more platforms & tools, rather than specific services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coordination between platforms Harmonisation between existing platforms
<p>EO products and service providers (<u>up & mid-stream</u>)</p> <p>Providers of essential EO products or services.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increasing number of missions & remote sensor development to support water quality observation(D2.5) Opportunity within the Copernicus Contributing Missions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demand for higher resolution products from end-users (D1.5, D2.2, D5.1) Demand for research to be translated into operational products (D3.3) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provision of very high resolution data from Copernicus Contributing Missions (D1.5, D2.2, D5.1) A multi-mission/multi-sensor (MM/MS) (D1.3, WP2) Establish feedback loops between Services and end-users (D3.3) Develop skilled team to translate research into operational products (D3.3)
<p>EO products and service providers (<u>downstream</u>)</p> <p>Providers of products or services that make full use of EO data and processing capabilities offered by data and platform providers.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increasing number of missions & remote sensor development to support inland water quality observation(D2.5) Possible reductions in cost of EO imagery Possible growing demand for EO-based services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demand for higher resolution products from end-users (D1.5, D2.2, D5.1) Demand for research to be translated into operational products (D3.3) Demand from feasible customers for products include evapotranspiration products Platforms designed for specific customers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development of digital Twins, Decision Support Systems, GIS-based knowledge management systems for decision making (WP1)
<p>Information providers</p> <p>Providers of sector-specific information that incorporates EO data along with non-EO data.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Growing trust and confidence by end-users in satellite-EO data (ref) Growing number of applications for EO, hence larger number of potential customers. Growing number of Platforms to access data. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gains from capacity building within sectors-specific education 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish a single catalogue User-friendly bot (D5.3) Promotion & awareness activities Capacity building for sector-specific groups (D1.5, Co-design of applications (D1.5) Co-development with water professionals (D3.3) Actionable information tools (D1.5) Harmonise existing products

5.2 Data providers

The Copernicus Programme is a data provider through the Copernicus Core services, and is also interested in promoting competitiveness with third-party providers. In particular, VHR, HR and MR data needs have been met from private offerings (e.g., Planet high resolution daily data) or by commercial products produced by the Copernicus Contributing Missions which covers 39 European Countries (D2.5). Data providers within the space industry are also largely impacted by the digital transformation, including new sensor advancements, transmission of data and cloud-computing services models (Daas) (European Parliament, 2016, D1.5). Downstream users are frequently expressing the need for higher resolution data (D2.2) demonstrating a constant demand for these products, whether they are delivered directly as part of the Copernicus core, enabling the downstream economy, or delivered by the private sector, stimulating competitiveness among data providers. In addition to higher resolution data, there is demand downstream for higher spectral band resolution, particularly for water quality concerns, which may drive a customer-base among environmental management and water utility sectors (D2.5, see Section 6). UAVs with hyperspectral radiometers are also a new form of data provider entering the market with large opportunities for local scale monitoring and collaboration with Copernicus core services (D4.4). Opportunities for in situ data providers are also evident, including the need for networks using citizen science and cal/val specific monitoring schemes (D4.2, D2.3).

5.3 Platform providers (front-end)

Platform providers are key to the uptake of EO data by making platforms through which users can utilise tools and capabilities to analyse EO data, develop algorithms and build applications. The platform provider segment, similarly to infrastructure and data providers, is heavily impacted by recent digital transformation and the shift towards cloud-based Platform as a Service (Paas). Platform providers offer cloud-based environments to work with data and range from general access platforms to more targeted platforms for specific users and are more front-end computing

services compared to infrastructure providers. Within the Copernicus Programme, access platforms are currently being provided by the Conventional Data Access Hubs Copernicus Open Access Hub, Copernicus Space Component Data Access (CSCDA), Copernicus Online Data Access (CODA) and EUMETCast, and more recently the addition of DIAS of 5 cloud-based platforms (See **D5.2** Section 5). More recently the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem is likely to become a massive access point, with around 600,000 current users. Partners involved in this are T systems, CloudFerro, Sinergise, VITO, ACRI-ST, DLR and RHEA.

In addition to technology drivers, there is also a push from end-users to create platforms that improve the ease of data access and reduce the capacity needed to access data. This was well documented in the many user engagement activities within Water-ForCE (**D3.1, D3.2, D5.1, D6.1**). Currently with many different access points to Copernicus data and products, access to data, format of data download etc can be improved. There is growing opportunity for Copernicus Programme and Services to improve their data access for end-users going directly to data, but there are also opportunities for downstream platform providers.

Some customers are certainly willing to pay for platforms that can reduce time, effort and knowledge required to use Earth observation data, and may increase trust of data. The EARSC survey [2022](#) highlighted that most of the companies surveyed were using Synergise Sentinel Hubs to access data at a subscription fee, and identified ease-to-access as a key reason, a message further emphasised in the Industry position paper [2022](#), and within **D3.4** for water managers. Downstream platform providers may find commercial success in tailoring directly to certain user needs, as well as providing specific downstream services. For example, there are large scope platforms which deliver data and information products directly for agricultural planning or precision irrigation.

Opportunities also exist for storing existing and growing in situ data used for cal/val and atmospheric correction (**D2.3, D2.4, D4.3**). In situ data collected by member states are stored in various different repositories, which have infrastructure and platform components. Additionally, a

number of open-access repositories (e.g. Pangaea, LDR and Zenodo) serve the community and are both infrastructure and platform providers. There are opportunities here in gathering and harmonising data, and hosting data in repositories that enable efficient uptake of in situ data for Earth observation products.

5.4 EO products and service providers

Upstream EO product and service providers comprises Copernicus Services where products and services are free and third-party providers, such as those within the Copernicus Contributing Missions, where products and services are delivered at a cost (see **D2.5**, **D3.3**). Alternatively downstream EO products and service providers may benefit from free products upstream by offering value-added services, and may also exploit opportunities resulting from gaps in the Copernicus Core Services. The EO product and services segment is largely driven by changes from upstream data providers, including the increasing number of satellite missions and remote sensor developments, which enable new products and services to be developed. For the Inland Water domain this is particularly related to the availability of new spectral bands (**D2.2** and **D2.5**) and higher spatial and temporal resolution (**D2.2**).

Activities from downstream EO service providers typically comprise the largest revenues within EO value chains (**D1.2**, **D1.5**, PwC, 2019, EUSPA, 2022). Downstream service can develop more specialised or local products and blending Copernicus and non-Copernicus input. The stability of the sector, however, is largely dependent on the continuity of current Copernicus products (**D3.4**, **D3.5**), and data remaining free to access (Position paper, 2022). Additionally, downstream EO service providers may compete with Copernicus Services as end-users may be able to access and process data directly from Copernicus Core and other data providers. A large number of specific products that are needed have been identified by sectors (**D1.5**) and different end users (see **D6.2**), only some of which will be delivered as commercial products. Some of the key products that have been recommended in Water-ForCE which have commercial feasibility as new products are; lake

and reservoir carbon content mapping to determine sufficient amounts of costly coagulants within the drinking water industry (**D2.2**, **D2.4**), water allocation modelling (**D3.4**), monitoring of groundwater aquifers (**WP1**, **D5.1**) flood and drought modelling for the insurance industry (**WP1**).

Downstream service providers may also offer platforms designed for specific communities. Key applications discussed in Water-ForCE (e.g platforms specifically for SDG and WFD monitoring- see **D6.1** for list, and **D3.3**) may not have commercial feasibility. Some key opportunities for platforms with a commercial customer base which are geared towards specific commercial end-user needs include platforms designed for agricultural users and to support flood-risk modelling for the insurance sector (See **Section 6**).

5.6 Information providers

Information providers offer sector-specific information incorporating EO data with non-EO data and are possibly the largest segment, if we use the overall EO trends shown in PwC market report 2020. Changes in this segment are driven by a growing customer base due to the increasing user of EO data in different end-user sectors (see **Section 6** of this report and **D1.4**). Additionally, there has been a noted growing trust and confidence in satellite data as stimulated through actions such as the Green Deal in 2019 (Position paper 2022). Results of the survey presented in **D6.3** also demonstrate strong confidence and interest in the abilities of EO in water quality and quantity data. Changes upstream will influence the segment also, in particular, improvements in digital access (**Section 6.3**), and increasing the supply of relevant products (**Section 6.4 and 6.5**) may also increase activity among EO-related Information providers within the inland water value chain. The Copernicus Programme can make a large impact on this sector through capacity building activities (**D6.3**), particularly those that increase awareness of EO applications to potential users and facilitate new users in resistant sectors. Practical steps towards improving on-boarding and new user experience are low-hanging fruit to stimulate this large segment of the value chain (**D5.3**, **D1.5**). These actions may also benefit upstream segments.

6. Opportunities driven by end-user needs

End-users are the final users of the Inland Water Value chain (**D1.5**, Section 2.1, see Figure 1), and benefit from the applications and services offered by information providers. End-users can also benefit from Copernicus products and Services when they access them directly (PwC, 2019). The emerging needs of end-users from different sectors (see **D1.2**) are indicative of opportunities that can be exploited upstream in the Inland Water value chain (**D1.4**). Opportunities for end-users can include new EO applications that solve existing problems in the sector or substantially improve existing processes, as well increase uptake of existing applications and greater reliance on EO data and services within a specific sector. The size and growth of the sector and attitude towards technical change are also important in assessing opportunities. End-user market can be very large and hence any contribution of Copernicus can result in large benefits. Furthermore, analysis in **D5.4** demonstrates that uptake of EO applications depends on the characteristics of the sector, in addition to the problem-solution fit. In this section each sector will be discussed in more detail including an outlook on the sector landscape using sources analysing the EO market at large and Water-ForCE analysis, a summary of the emerging applications identified in **D14** and identification of the opportunities within the sector sourced from **Water-ForCE work packages 1-5**, finally with a note on the possible role which Copernicus can play in the sector. Note that focus here is on commercial viability and industry-based applications rather than research.

Table 3. Summary of key end-user sectors using analysis of sectors in *D1.2* and *D1.4*, recommendations from *WP1-5* and external sources. (See high resolution image of table 3 [HERE](#))

	Sector context	Commercial end-users	Overview of emerging EO applications	Opportunities identified for the sector	Actions within the Copernicus Programme				
 Key customer of water domain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biggest user sector and increasing compliance demand from new Common Agricultural Policy, Groundwater Directive, etc. Agriculture accounts for 70% of water use Agriculture is a key source of water pollution and water wastage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Farmers Agricultural cooperatives Paying agencies / public authorities (national, regional) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water management (i.e., precision irrigation and smart farming services) Drought monitoring (e.g., soil moisture monitoring) Indicators or agricultural impacts (e.g., increase in algae) 	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>General</td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regional scale data at high spatial resolution (1-2m) Temporal resolution from weekly to daily Irrigation monitoring tools </td> </tr> <tr> <td>Products</td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> CDOM products Yield production combined with water availability and soil moisture Evapotranspiration Water stress Wetness indicators Inland water features (e.g., ditches) Rivulets, streams and small water bodies Fertilizer pollution indicators Crop water needs </td> </tr> </table>	General	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regional scale data at high spatial resolution (1-2m) Temporal resolution from weekly to daily Irrigation monitoring tools 	Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CDOM products Yield production combined with water availability and soil moisture Evapotranspiration Water stress Wetness indicators Inland water features (e.g., ditches) Rivulets, streams and small water bodies Fertilizer pollution indicators Crop water needs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provider of high spatial resolution data Provision of local, regional and global products for monitoring & decision-making Facilitate shift to sustainable agriculture at local level through funding grants Work with downstream EO, platform and information providers Support uptake of EO in legislations including CAP
General	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regional scale data at high spatial resolution (1-2m) Temporal resolution from weekly to daily Irrigation monitoring tools 								
Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CDOM products Yield production combined with water availability and soil moisture Evapotranspiration Water stress Wetness indicators Inland water features (e.g., ditches) Rivulets, streams and small water bodies Fertilizer pollution indicators Crop water needs 								
 Large public customer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access to clean water is a major concern (UN SDG6) Water services can be both public and private ownership Strongly related to agriculture industry as the main pollutant to drinking water. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Paying agencies / public authorities (national, regional) Water companies (drinking & waste) Infrastructure companies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water monitoring EO to complement on-site approach Ground and surface water assessment 	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>General</td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Drinking water quality and quantity Cyanobacterial harmful algal bloom occurrence and frequency monitoring tools Information to monitor ground water Long-term precipitation and streamflow </td> </tr> <tr> <td>Products</td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> DOC and CDOM concentrations Nitrate concentration Turbidity product Real-time precipitation and evapotranspiration Near real-time water levels Near real-time soil moisture Precipitation forecasts Groundwater storage changes </td> </tr> </table>	General	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Drinking water quality and quantity Cyanobacterial harmful algal bloom occurrence and frequency monitoring tools Information to monitor ground water Long-term precipitation and streamflow 	Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DOC and CDOM concentrations Nitrate concentration Turbidity product Real-time precipitation and evapotranspiration Near real-time water levels Near real-time soil moisture Precipitation forecasts Groundwater storage changes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support for public water supplies through research projects Provide key products such as monitoring ground-water aquifers Support uptake of EO in legislations including WFD & Drinking Water Directive
General	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Drinking water quality and quantity Cyanobacterial harmful algal bloom occurrence and frequency monitoring tools Information to monitor ground water Long-term precipitation and streamflow 								
Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DOC and CDOM concentrations Nitrate concentration Turbidity product Real-time precipitation and evapotranspiration Near real-time water levels Near real-time soil moisture Precipitation forecasts Groundwater storage changes 								
 Uptake resistance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Large use sector with economic importance Includes both oil and gas, and renewable energy Difficult market to implement change, traditional Volatility in energy prices can prevent investment in new technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Private energy companies Renewable energy companies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Flow and water quantity modelling for hydropower management Determining electricity rates EO for flood monitoring in disaster prevention 	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>General</td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information about inflow to hydropower reservoirs Monitoring of water recharge to reservoirs Integration of climate variables </td> </tr> <tr> <td>Products</td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Precipitation products Daily/weekly/monthly inflow forecasts and scenarios Water quantity products at reservoir scale </td> </tr> </table>	General	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information about inflow to hydropower reservoirs Monitoring of water recharge to reservoirs Integration of climate variables 	Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Precipitation products Daily/weekly/monthly inflow forecasts and scenarios Water quantity products at reservoir scale 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coordination with energy sector including increasing awareness of EO data potentials Investment in modelling applications for hydropower
General	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information about inflow to hydropower reservoirs Monitoring of water recharge to reservoirs Integration of climate variables 								
Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Precipitation products Daily/weekly/monthly inflow forecasts and scenarios Water quantity products at reservoir scale 								
 Diverse customer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> An umbrella sector for various activities & sectors Specific markets, scope for micro companies A large number of realised and potential EO applications Good uptake Diverse customer base Spin-off from research Industry at large needs support in Green transformation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Paying agencies / public authorities (national, regional) Aquafarmers & fisheries Infrastructure / urban planning companies Engineering companies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coastal monitoring Monitoring threats to ecosystems Biodiversity modelling Aquafarming planning Coastal water quality & conditions 	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>General</td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water continuum products (D5.2) Develop automated monitoring system including coastal water types (D2.3, D4.3) Im proved atmospheric correction algorithms for coastal water systems (D2.2) Water quality and quantity products in general Monitoring of coastal and inland water biodiversity </td> </tr> <tr> <td>Products</td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> High level biogeochemical products (primary production etc) Soil characteristics and soil moisture Fish shoals & benthic algae mapping, eutrophication, pollution etc. Bathymetry maps Coastal conditions forecasting products Detection of unregulated and illegal fishing Near-real-time data to protect nursery zones Water demand at various scales Modelling of water budget Evaporation and transpiration Runoff and inflows </td> </tr> </table>	General	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water continuum products (D5.2) Develop automated monitoring system including coastal water types (D2.3, D4.3) Im proved atmospheric correction algorithms for coastal water systems (D2.2) Water quality and quantity products in general Monitoring of coastal and inland water biodiversity 	Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High level biogeochemical products (primary production etc) Soil characteristics and soil moisture Fish shoals & benthic algae mapping, eutrophication, pollution etc. Bathymetry maps Coastal conditions forecasting products Detection of unregulated and illegal fishing Near-real-time data to protect nursery zones Water demand at various scales Modelling of water budget Evaporation and transpiration Runoff and inflows 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support for start-ups, SME's and micro-companies Support for research spin-offs (financial & capacity building) Support uptake of EO in legislations Develop water continuum products
General	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water continuum products (D5.2) Develop automated monitoring system including coastal water types (D2.3, D4.3) Im proved atmospheric correction algorithms for coastal water systems (D2.2) Water quality and quantity products in general Monitoring of coastal and inland water biodiversity 								
Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High level biogeochemical products (primary production etc) Soil characteristics and soil moisture Fish shoals & benthic algae mapping, eutrophication, pollution etc. Bathymetry maps Coastal conditions forecasting products Detection of unregulated and illegal fishing Near-real-time data to protect nursery zones Water demand at various scales Modelling of water budget Evaporation and transpiration Runoff and inflows 								
 Large growth potential	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Large economic importance due to consequences of economic loss Large current and potential investment from insurance domain (as customer and developer) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Insurance companies Development banks Paying ministries / agencies and weather services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Flooded areas delineation Damage assessment on relative infrastructure Changes in water levels Water dynamics Coastal erosion Modelling and forecasting focus Insurance models 	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>General</td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Early warning systems for floods and in particular for coastal floods Monitoring of industrial pressure on inland water bodies Nutrient pollution alert systems Flood prevention and flood risk management </td> </tr> <tr> <td>Products</td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water quality and water levels (quantity) at catchment scale Total water storage in dams & reservoirs Drought related products: forecasting, prevention and management Real-time weather conditions for extreme event prediction </td> </tr> </table>	General	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Early warning systems for floods and in particular for coastal floods Monitoring of industrial pressure on inland water bodies Nutrient pollution alert systems Flood prevention and flood risk management 	Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water quality and water levels (quantity) at catchment scale Total water storage in dams & reservoirs Drought related products: forecasting, prevention and management Real-time weather conditions for extreme event prediction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote synergies between CEMS and Land service, as well as with relevant water communities of practise Facilitate and support modelling community within Copernicus Collaboration with green insurance, capacity building or knowledge share between industry & research
General	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Early warning systems for floods and in particular for coastal floods Monitoring of industrial pressure on inland water bodies Nutrient pollution alert systems Flood prevention and flood risk management 								
Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water quality and water levels (quantity) at catchment scale Total water storage in dams & reservoirs Drought related products: forecasting, prevention and management Real-time weather conditions for extreme event prediction 								

6.1 Agriculture

Water is an essential production resource in agriculture and the sector is a growing end-user of EO data. The sector offers many commercially viable opportunities for inland water based uses of satellite-EO data but demands high resolution products offered at a local level.

Market Context: Agriculture is the largest current user sector for Copernicus products and Services and end-users in the Agriculture sector receive the most benefits of the Programme including €318 million Copernicus enabled revenue in 2018. In terms of the EO market of data and services, agriculture comprises ~13% of the market and is on a steady growth rate (EUSPA, 2022). Agriculture is closely related to the water domain as the main consumer of water in the EU (EEA, 2017) is from the agriculture industry and water is an essential production resource. Existing policies including the new 2019 Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), are increasing pressure in the sector to use innovative climate-smart applications, including EO to preserve and manage water use within agriculture (see **D1.2**; “Future of Food and Farming, 2017, **D1.3**). Agriculture is also addressed in the Sustainable Development Goals including SDG1 and SDG12 (**D1.4**, **D1.6**).

Opportunities: Many applications of EO in agriculture are related to water allocation, irrigation planning, and monitoring water wastage or pollution from fertilisers (**D1.2**, **D1.4**). EO-based coastal monitoring can also be related to protecting agricultural land (**D1.2**). A key emerging need within the sector is for very high resolution products for smart farming services and precision irrigation (i.e., fieldscale; 5-2m spatial resolution, daily temporal resolution) (**D1.5**, **D3.5**). In addition to VHR EO-satellite data, airborne drones can also deliver information on irrigation needs, soil moisture and water-stress of crops, at the local scale or an individual farm (**D2.3**, **D4.4**). The uptake of these technologies and their commercial viability, however, relies on their ability to reduce costs and save time / effort over traditional approaches to farming. Gap analysis of Copernicus products and services identified various products, including repeat requirement for evapotranspiration products which is required at a 5-10 m pixel resolution (**D3.5**, **D5.2**). This is an essential parameter for water

stress estimation and for modelling applications. Global and regional products relating to water use, soil salinisation, sedimentation, nutrients and evapotranspiration are also needed for national planning, food security analysis at governmental and regional levels, which influence the market through predicting food security, determining the environmental impact of agriculture, policy making and setting food prices (D1.3, D5.2).

Role of Copernicus: Considering that agricultural applications require very high resolution products, continued increase of spatial resolution, even at a price, will likely increase uptake of EO within the sector. Sentinel-3 products are too coarse for field-scale variability (D3.5). Alternatively, reducing the costs of high spatial resolution products could promote greater uptake of EO among end-users and may promote sustainable agricultural goals or improve the profitability of the sector. Particular products that could be offered at higher resolution include evapotranspiration, water stress and soil moisture (Table 3, D3.5, D5.2).

Copernicus may also play a role in improving the uptake of EO- applications in agriculture at local scales or by individual farmers, for water management. Actions towards this include building awareness and engagement among farmers (see D6.1 on capacity building), and supporting business innovation or delivery of Farm advisory services and platforms designed for agricultural end-users (e.g., D1.3; see [Sinergise](#), [Envsys](#), [Irrisat Project](#)), incorporating airborne drone data with higher resolution Sentinel products (see [3edata](#)), as well as the inclusion of “Earth Observation”, “Remote sensing” and “Space” within existing CAP legislation (D1.3, D3.5).

6.2 Drinking water, utilities, water allocation & urban water management

Drinking water utilities and urban development are large and essential sectors that could benefit from greater uptake of EO data but may lack commercial customers.

Market Context: There is a very good fit with EO applications for Inland water and the drinking water and utilities sector, which includes providers of drinking water, urban allocation of water and waste sewage treatment. Demand for monitoring of drinking water is also driven by the need to provide access to safe water, sanitation and hygiene for all (Sustainable Development Goal 6 - **D1.6**). In the EU, 20% of surface water is threatened by pollution and the number of people and areas affected by water scarcity and drought has increased by 20% in the past 30 years (**D1.2**, Value of Water, 2017). There is also a strong relationship to agriculture which is the largest water user in the EU (Water Europe, [2017](#)). Although drinking water and utilities are not included in Copernicus' market report (PwC, 2019) urban monitoring, including urban water management, received €24 million in 2018. Sector is not represented in EUSPA market report 2022, but related sectors urban development, infrastructure, and maritime and waterways are all set to grow at roughly the market average. Currently, drinking water and utilities are predominantly a concern of public authorities, or a collaboration between private and public bodies. However, it has been estimated that EU member states need to increase annual expenditure between 20% and 170% to meet compliance with EU water directives, for which commercial investment may be needed (OECD, [2020](#)). Shifts towards a smart-water society in policy are also likely to promote new digital water technologies (**D1.2**; Value of Water, 2017).

Opportunities: There are many opportunities to use EO data for supplementing on-site monitoring programmes and to inform water allocation between irrigation, the pollution caused by agriculture, and citizen access for water in smart cities (**D1.2**). EO applications can also be used to reduce costs

(e.g., determine the amount of coagulants needed; **D2.2, D2.4**) or ensure that the pricing of water reflects the true value of water locally (**D1.3**).

The demands on EO are for higher resolution, localised and water body discretized products (**D3.5, D5.4**). Specific products for use within this sector that are currently missing from Copernicus portfolio include 1) carbon related products (e.g., dissolved organic carbon (DOC), total organic carbon (TOC), CO₂) (**D2.4, D4.5**), 2) shallow water products (e.g., bathymetry, benthic cover, benthic habitat type, benthic disturbance), and 3) surface material products (e.g., plastic and other litter, floating cyanobacteria, water hyacinth, macroalgae (e.g., Sargassum or Ulva), pollen) (**D2.4**). In particular, the drinking water industry has a need to detect dissolved organic matter, and also is a new user of localised carbon products which alter the taste of water and is one of the hardest parts of water treatment (**D2.4**). Additionally, uptake within the sector is predicted for products that can be used to monitor ground-water aquifers (**D1.4, D5.1, D5.3**) and for tools to detect harmful algal bloom and agricultural pollutants with early warning systems, or for detection leaks in supply systems, which are already commercially distributed (**D1.1**). All water quality applications will be greatly enhanced by increased validation (**D2.5, D5.2, D2.2**) and new optical missions (e.g. CHIME), to be designed specifically for inland water, including lakes and reservoirs (**D2.4**). There are also opportunities within the sector for data providers offering higher spatial resolution data for water extent monitoring (**D3.5**). Notably, there are large capacity barriers for water managers and therefore applications which are coupled with capacity building for water managers are also likely to have greater uptake (**D3.4, D6.1**).

Role of the Copernicus Programme: Various member states will need support in meeting EU drinking water regulations, which may include commercial investment and blended finance vehicles (OECD, [2020](#)). Copernicus can directly support the sector through the provision of relevant products, particularly for water quality parameters (e.g., DOM and CDOM) at high resolution, through ensuring these products are available in Copernicus Contributing Missions (**D2.2**) or by funding relevant research projects such as the H2020 WQEMS project, where researchers deliver products directly for the water utilities industry (**D1.6, D2.2**). These projects additionally improve capacity

among water managers and are therefore likely to increase uptake of existing commercial applications (D6.1).

6.3. Energy (Oil & Gas, Renewable Energies)

Energy is a split market, oil & gas is resistant to change but there are some opportunities which could result in large revenues. Hydropower is also a large market that could make further use of EO within water quality modelling.

Market Context: Energy is a large and important market globally and hence any use of EO data within the sector, particularly within the oil and gas sector, has large economic potential (D1.4). In 2018, Copernicus enabled revenues were €417 million euros within the oil and gas sector and €137 million euros within renewable energies (PwC, 2019). The oil and gas sector is particularly resistant to the uptake of new technology due to volatility in energy prices (PwC, 2019). A shift towards renewable energy is necessary to meet the sustainable development goal 7 for Affordable and clean energy (D1.6). Applications may be more heavily related to water quantity monitoring but policy changes may hold energy companies more responsible for their impact downstream and this increases their interest in water quality monitoring.

Opportunities: EO applications within oil and gas including monitoring of coastal ecosystems, marine habitats, pollutants, during exploration and drilling activities (D1.2, D1.4). EO applications also include modelling hazards and risk including floods and coastal currents (D5.2), and also monitoring the impact of mining on water quality downstream (see environmental monitoring or raw materials sectors for more on this). Hydropower also has opportunities for use of EO data related to water quantity modelling to determine energy production, incorporating EO products for surface water conditions, flow and water level (D5.2). Opportunity exists for EO providers offering precipitation, soil moisture, evapotranspiration, surface runoff, inland water temperature, bathymetry, DEM and water level, at daily and high spatial resolution products (D3.3, D5.2). Provision of hourly products for flood extent, discharge and temperature may also advance modelling capacities and uptake within the hydropower sector (D5.2), as well as the provision of snow and ice extent products 0-1000m and ground water recharge at hourly or daily frequencies (D3.5). Following this, there are also

opportunities for downstream EO service providers to deliver specialised models or actionable tools for hydropower reservoirs.

Role of the Copernicus Programme: Copernicus can take various actions to improve the penetration of EO data within the energy sector at large. Specifically, this may involve improving the transfer of knowledge with relevant research institutions / projects, and co-development with the sector to curate products specifically for the sector that can be delivered commercially (D3.3). Investment in hydrological modelling capacities within copernicus, and the provision of higher resolution data for this purpose, may advance the shift towards renewable energies (D5.2).

6.4. Environmental accounting, assurance compliance, and ESG's

Environmental management is a diverse sector with many different customers. The sector is relatively small and has low growth forecasted, but with high environmental benefits.

Market Context: Environmental monitoring, including coastal, river and biodiversity monitoring, as a broad sector is important for the management of water resources and is also increasingly in demand for environmental compliance assurance, environmental accounting and assessing ESG performance of businesses (EUSPA, 2022). Hence the value chain includes the collection of environmental data to information service providers, such as [Deltares](#), who deliver information ready for reporting or decision making. The sector growth is strongly coupled with EU policy evolution and the 'greening' of investment (See Box 3). In the UK, mandatory biodiversity net gain will influence the market as biodiversity units can be bought and sold. ESG performance is increasingly being used as a way to assess businesses by investors, customers, suppliers and other stakeholders. Customers for this sector include a vast number of other sectors (e.g., agriculture), who are required to meet regulations and assess their footprint on the water environment. There are various paying public customers (e.g., agencies and ministries responsible for river and coastal management, biodiversity, ecosystem protection) but also a diverse number of private customers (e.g., sustainable investment companies, aqua farmers and tourism providers). Customers also include finance companies that want to improve the ESG performance of their portfolios or businesses at large. The delivery of services within this sector may include many public-private collaborations, micro-companies or research spin-off projects.

The environmental monitoring sector (excluding forest-related carbon monitoring), comprises less than 5% of the EO data and service revenues and growth is predicted to be below market average for the EO industry between 2021 and 2031 (EUSPA, 2022). Currently inland and coastal waters do not play a major role in environmental accounting, and have largely been missing from the existing carbon markets. However, important changes will likely increase the need for water-related

environmental monitoring and accounting. For example in the UK, biodiversity net credits have just been introduced to incentivise the protection of water bodies, where credits can be created by reducing or capturing nutrients upstream (bcplaw, [2023](#)).

Opportunities: EO applications within the sector closely related to applications discussed, particularly those within water utilities for water quality monitoring (**D2.4**). Provision of high resolution products, water quality and surface water parameters, improved validation of water quality products are all likely to increase opportunities within the sector. With the technical provisions in place, opportunities for new business models, created by EU water policy, trends towards sustainable investment techniques, and new financing structures, can be exploited. Examples include the AGRI3 Fund, demonstrating a use of public funding to mobilise commercial finance for water investment into EO applications addressing SDGs including SDG 6 (OECD, [2020](#)). Policy that incentivises water body performance, such as with carbon offset programs, could increase financial viability of applications such as [AquaRating](#). The Green Deal will also align financial markets with development goals, promoting the ESG process as a key tool for investment, hence applications of biodiversity indicators or planforms directly for this, may capitalise on this shift (Copernicus, [2023](#)).

Role of Copernicus: Copernicus programme can enable the Environmental Monitoring sector through future sentinels with water quality monitoring objectives (**D2.5**), improved inland and coastal products, namely the provision of higher resolution products, missing water quality and surface water parameters (Section 6.2; **D2.4**), and improved validation of water quality products for inland and coastal systems (**D5.2**). Given the size and slower growth of the sector, as well as the environmental benefits of the sector and importance in implementing policy, the private sector may need mobilisation through public funding. Although the Green Deal is key in driving the sector (Copernicus, [2023](#)), policy may also increase explicit recommendation and application of EO within EU water policies (Industry Position paper, 2022).

6.5. Health

There are massive social benefits to advancing the use of EO within the health sector, as well as economic benefits for the downstream providers who deliver these services. Opportunities for water-related EO applications include monitoring risk and supporting preparedness to water-borne disease outbreaks.

Context: Water is intrinsically important for public health, starting with access to clean water and sanitation (SDG6). Contaminated water and insufficient sanitation cause around 1.6 million deaths per year, with many of these deaths in children under 5 years old. This sector is closely related to the utilities and sanitation sectors, additionally the agriculture sector is typically the largest polluter of water and thus a massive pressure on public health. National and international health authorities have a massive interest in monitoring inland and coastal water to monitor the threats to human health and to support preparedness for waterborne diseases. Earth observation is a very useful tool in monitoring water and can be combined with other health-related indicators or integrated into health risk modelling and mapping. Existing examples include [EO4HEALTH](#) initiative which supports many [projects](#).

Opportunities: There are massive remaining opportunities for EO within the health sector. These include integrating EO-derived inland and coastal water quality information into mapping water-born diseases (e.g., leptospirosis, cholera) and pathogen and toxin risk maps. Inland water quantity and condition are also key for understanding mosquito habitats and predicting the spread of diseases through mosquitoes. Monitoring and early warning systems of harmful algal blooms are also in increasing demand by authorities who are responsible for mitigation and warning . Harmful algal blooms are currently tracked using Chl-a as a proxy for phycocyanin, so new sensors that include 620 nm are key to monitoring algal blooms. Additionally, higher resolution optical measurements which allow for monitoring of small inland water bodies or intricacies of coastal conditions may also increase the accuracy of models for health purposes. New applications may

also include understanding the relationship between healthy water bodies and societal wellbeing. The benefactors of this are civil society and benefits might be most impactful outside of Europe, and in meeting the Sustainable Development goals. Many of these opportunities may be delivered by a combination of downstream EO providers and consultancies who then advise local or national agencies, and hence there are economic benefits for Europe, as well as the inherent social benefits.

Role of Copernicus: Given the importance of public health and the potential social and economic costs incurred by health outbreak, there is a clear benefit to investing heavily in applications which can reduce health risk and can increase preparedness. The Copernicus Programme can play a role in increasing the collection of essential data (i.e. high spatial resolution and more water quality products), while also promoting the funding of research projects which advance the science of health risk mapping, such as EO4Health, Blue Planet and AquaWatch. The [Copernicus Health Hub](#) already demonstrates a clear goal of Copernicus to enable the health sector to leverage Earth Observation capacities. Future collaboration between the Copernicus Health Hub with inland and coastal water communities of practice could be supported in the future. Although the main customer base for public health applications are public bodies, there is still substantial opportunity for downstream providers to develop improved and commercialised water products for use in national or international health monitoring.

6.6. Insurance for Natural Disasters

Insurance for natural disasters is a growing market which has strong links with EO applications and modelling, penetration of Copernicus products in this growth can have massive revenues.

Market Context: Insurance and Natural disasters is an important domain with large revenue potential but low penetration of Copernicus products. The Market share of the Insurance sector in 2021 was ~5%, and is predicted to be ~15% by 2031, well above the EO market average (EUSPA, 2022). In 2018, however, the penetration of Copernicus data within the sector was less than 1% and Copernicus enabled revenue was the lowest sector analysed at 14 million (PwC, 2018). There are many EO applications within modelling of water-related hazards including floods and droughts (D3.4, D5.2). Hazards and emergencies are typically a public authorities concern, and Copernicus Emergency management Service (CEMS) already offers operational application of EO data. The insurance and risk sector is closely related with a huge financial customer base.

Opportunities: Key applications include hydrological modelling whereby EO products such as flow and water level products are combined with hydrological modelling (D5.2). Key products to increase opportunities in the sector closely relate to those mentioned for the hydropower sector, for high resolution modelling in detailed or regional hydrodynamic, river and water balance models (see Section 7.3). Downstream EO providers have opportunities to deliver more specialised products using models which can delineate flooded areas, detect and monitor changes in water levels (D5.2, D3.4). Further along the value chain, there are opportunities for information providers to use these products to directly inform the insurance industry on the level of destruction due to flooding events within hours, so they can rapidly assess the damage to their insured assets, avoiding unnecessary delays and costs by conducting field investigations (D1.5). It is also likely that such applications and modelling will be done within insurance companies themselves.

Role of Copernicus: Copernicus has the potential to massively increase penetration of EO within the sector and exploit large revenue, by aligning existing research activities with industry-based needs. This could be achieved through coordinating networks, for example between CEMS, communities of practice (e.g., **D5.1** working group) and the insurance industry. This collaboration and inclusion of research may also stimulate positive environmental benefits, such as the uptake of nature-based solutions (e.g., protecting ecosystems which help mitigate risk; see OECD, [2020](#)). This may also improve the stakeholder representation of the insurance sector within the water domain **(D1.1)**.

6.7. Indigenous-led water management

Indigenous peoples can benefit from EO-derived information and indigenous communities play a role in shaping the EO field.

Context: Indigenous people manage water-related challenges with traditional knowledge and solutions, and have contributed greatly to protecting water bodies around the world. Indigenous people have been managing water bodies since time immemorial and the knowledge passed through generations is essential in understanding changes in our water bodies due to climate change and anthropogenic activities (UNESCO, [2023](#)). Furthermore, indigenous peoples often have a holistic understanding of water, which may be missing from the mainstream commodification of water and can be a model for understanding the true value of water. By many indigenous communities, water is considered a sentient being and considered interrelationality with the needs of all other living things (SIWI, [2023](#)). Service to water bodies is also regarded as a healing process for stewards, particularly from the traumas of colonisation and dissociation from the land (Indigenous Land Stewardship Circle, [2023](#)). In certain parts of the world, indigenous people are acquiring sovereignty over stolen lands, which results in the return of management rights over inland and coastal waters. As challenges of managing water increase due to climate change, pollution and urban development, EO applications may be a useful tool for monitoring and decision making. For example, women from the Samburu tribe in Kenya use satellite images to mark out boundaries, to track resources and determine water quality or contamination (Space4Water, [2023](#)). Another application of water-related EO for indigenous communities may be the tracking of illegal activities, typically through land monitoring, but also from changes in water quality (e.g., turbid plumes from mining) and quantity (e.g. illegal extraction of water).

The knowledge and representation of indigenous communities is essential to the global water domain, but indigenous voices, especially those of indigenous women who are often responsible and stewards for water within their communities, have been poorly represented (OHCHR, [2019](#)).

Indigenous peoples have been underrepresented in international governing bodies, and have limited access to technology or capacity to use EO. In recent years, a number of research projects and international initiatives are helping to fill this gap, including EO4IM (Earth observation for indigenous-led land management), and Indigenous voices within the [EO4SPACE](#) initiative. International groups such as [UNWater](#), ACARE (African Center for Aquatic Research and Education) and WWQA (World Water Quality Alliance) are also focused on enabling indigenous water forums, and making space for indigenous voices within discussions around water.

Opportunities: There are many more opportunities for indigenous communities to further the uptake of EO within their water management and stewardship activities. Importantly, this should be driven by the needs of the communities themselves and not replicate colonial power dynamics where western or mainstream educators define the agenda. Hence many of the opportunities in this sector will be centered around informed capacity building, which might include the provision of technical resources, training sessions and delivery of downstream products which directly meet the needs of indigenous peoples. Projects which are cross-directional knowledge transfers can also benefit the water domain at large, where scientists can learn from indigenous knowledge about the history and management of water bodies and future management approaches.

Role of Copernicus: The key role of the Copernicus Programme for this is the provision of EO data and services, as well as the continued commitment to improving the ease of access for data access. Since the Copernicus Programme already offers EO data and products this is a massive service to the water domain, including for indigenous communities and removal of the barriers to the uptake of the knowledge attained through EO should be the next priority. One existing barrier might be lack of certainty of water-related EO products for regions of relevance to indigenous communities, which require more dedicated calibration and validation. Data access and organisational structure is certainly eurocentric which could exclude indigenous communities. Funding is necessary to initiate projects which increase the voice of indigenous communities or demonstrate indigenous-led water management practises using EO. In particular, projects of most value are those which enable the

stewardship of indigenous women and retain the authority of indigenous communities to manage their water bodies and ensure clean water and sanitation for their community.

6.8. Mining & Raw materials

Mining is one of the main polluters of water and the sector is increasingly demanded to demonstrate impact on water quality. Hence there is large potential for EO within the sector

Context: Mining is a highly profitable sector responsible for the extraction of minerals and can have many impacts on water quantity (e.g., reducing water discharge) and water quality (e.g., polluting water downstream). Companies are increasingly responsible for assessing the environmental impacts on life cycle stages from the exploration phase to mine closure and aftercare. This sector is related to environmental monitoring. The use of EO within the sector is relatively mature, comprehensively analysed by EUSPA in “Report on Energy & Raw Materials” [2022](#), and projects such as Earth observation for the Mining of Raw Materials ([EO4RM](#)) led by Deltares. Recent report by Digital Earth Australia (DEA) also addresses the key benefits of EO for the sector (DEA, [2021](#)).

Opportunities: There are large opportunities for the downstream sector to deliver tailored products and platforms that reduce capacity, effort and build confidence within the mining sector end-users (DEA, [2021](#)). Downstream sector willing to fully incorporate EO within existing mining processes, who can understand the influence on downstream processes (e.g., understand the different uncertainty of EO-derived information). Where EO can clearly reduce risk.

Role of Copernicus: Copernicus-enabled revenues would be largely increased by even small increases in EO applications within the mining and raw materials sector. Hence there is a clear opportunity for the Copernicus Programme to implement projects that further invest in the needs of the sector, coordinate collaborations between EO scientists and industry experts, and co-develop products that streamline into existing processes for the full life cycle. This appears to be a sector with large commercial potential either directly for the Copernicus Programme or to be delivered by downstream providers.

6.9. Transport

Inland waterways offer a massive opportunity to reduce carbon emissions from transportation. EO will play a critical role in this transition.

Context: Inland waterway transport has been explored as a competitive alternative to road and rail (EC, [2016](#)). Advantages over other transportation is the reliability, lower energy emissions, and less congestion. The transition to inland waterways could contribute a significant portion to energy emission cuts, with estimates at 17% of road transport and 50% of rail transport. Typically this form of transportation has less safety risks and can improve conditions within cities. Within Europe there is large amount of waterway connectivity between Member States, with around 37,000 km of navigable waterways (EPthinktank, [2023](#)). Hence, inland waterways and the inland transportation sector is included under the European Green Deal and the EU's sustainable and smart mobility strategy. Current challenges for the sector include becoming greener to reduce unnecessary emissions, showing resilience to climate change (particularly floods and droughts). The outlook for the future suggests large public and private investment into 'smart' technology and infrastructure, such as ports. The objectives for the sector are outlined in the European NAIADES III Programme (2021-2027). Given the international support and Green Deal focus on decarbonisation of the transport sector, there is a large growth in the capacity of the sector predicted.

Opportunities: The application of EO within the inland water transport network is already incorporated into the navigation sector (EUSPA, [2022](#)) but will likely need to expand as the sector shifts towards 'smart' technology. Extreme low and high flow rates are problematic for inland waterway navigation and are one of the main applications of EO within the sector. This is both important in understanding up-to-date monitoring of waterways, as well as predicting the future impacts of climate change on the inland waterways network which might inform future investment decisions. Further projects demonstrate other applications which are likely to have more commercial and public advantages are incorporation of EO with modelling to increase the accuracy

of navigation information and the safety of waterway transport, early warning systems, monitoring of spillages and water quality issues, better digitalisation of navigation through platforms to tools which bring together multiple sources of information, capacity building to ensure that transport managers can fully capitalise on the information retrieved from satellites Earth observation.

Role of Copernicus: Given the focus on water quality products, Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-3 are both important in the provision of relevant data and products for monitoring inland waterways, particularly in terms of altimetry. The quality of such products has been particularly well validated (ESA, [2023](#), D5.2). Advancements in this topic may particularly come from [the operational service for the water sector](#), within the copernicus Climate Change Service (CS3).

7. Strategy for Copernicus Programme business opportunities

7.1 Key actions for the Copernicus Programme

For simplicity, the priority actions emerging from this document are presented below;

1. **Increase the visibility of the inland water value chain-** The lack of recognition of the inland water value chain is evident in Copernicus market reports (**Section 3.2**). Quantifying and investigating the EO-based inland water value chain is necessary to understand the importance of the market within Europe, globally and over time.
2. **Include the use of Earth Observation explicitly in policy** - EO needs to be brought into policy, with clear guidelines/compliance, with relation to specific regulations. In addition, there are benefits from considering the indicators that can be measured using EO products when developing new policy or policy evolution.
3. **Enhance in situ component to increase trust** - The lack of in situ data and subsequent lack of product validation is frequently an issue for many downstream providers and end-user sectors. Improving the availability of in situ data to validate products would greatly increase the social, economic and environmental benefits of the Copernicus Programme.
4. **Deliver high spatial and temporal resolution data, even at a cost** - The need for high spatiotemporal resolution is inherent to inland and coastal applications, since they can cover small areas and have high temporal variability. Hence, higher resolution products are predicted to be met with enthusiasm in all sectors and some sectors will be willing to pay.
5. **Pledge for data continuity** - Downstream EO services and information services comprise a large portion of the revenues of the whole value chain and their business planning relies on the continued provision of data and products.
6. **Deliver commercial products to sectors that are willing to pay** - Small changes can result in large benefits for certain high-benefit sections. In particular, the insurance sector is a

massive new customer for EO-data and the energy sector is very large and could incorporate EO applications (**Sections 6.3 and 6.5**). Even small increases in the uptake of EO applications within these sectors could generate large economic benefits for Copernicus and the EU. Products can be co-developed with relevant sectors.

7. **Support end-users with highest societal benefits** - Support (through start-up funding, subsidised products etc) are required for new innovative applications of Copernicus data and products within the water domain, particularly initiatives which are promoted in the EU Green Deal. These might be commercial (e.g., new business models increasing or non-commercial).
8. **Focus on awareness and the skills gap** - The skills gap is recognised as one of the main factors holding back the European downstream EO sector (EARSC, 2021). Furthermore, the penetration of EO among enduser sectors is still relatively low, with awareness being one of the main reasons. Addressing this is discussed in D6.1 but it is likely that increasing the presence of Earth Observation within formalised education will improve this.

References

All deliverables from the Water-ForCE project are found on: <https://waterforce.eu/documents-and-deliverables> (accessed 11 July 2023).

Directorate General for Internal Policies, 2016, Space Market Uptake in Europe, accessed 11 July 2023, [https://esamultimedia.esa.int/docs/business_with_esa/IPOL_STU\(2016\)569984_EN.pdf](https://esamultimedia.esa.int/docs/business_with_esa/IPOL_STU(2016)569984_EN.pdf).

EARSC, 2020, Industry Survey 2020, accessed 11 July 2023, <https://earsc.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/Industry-survey-2020.pdf>.

EARSC, 2021, Industry Survey 2020, accessed 11 July 2023, <https://earsc.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/EARSC-Industry-survey-2021.pdf>.

EARSC, 2022, A survey into the State & Health of the European EO Services Industry 2022, accessed 11 July 2023, <https://earsc.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/Industry-survey-2022-final-version-12-1.pdf>.

EARSC, 2022, Industry View of the Future of Copernicus, accessed 11 July 2023, https://earsc.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/20220901_Copernicus-Evolution-Position-paper.pdf.

EARSC, 2019, Industry View of the Future of the Copernicus Programme: key issues to address, accessed 11 July 2023, https://earsc.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/Copernicus-evolution-POSITION-PAPER-FINAL_20191114.pdf.

EUSPA, 2022, EO and GNSS: Market Report, accessed 11 July 2023, https://www.euspa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/uploads/euspa_market_report_2022.pdf.

Global Navigation Satellite Systems Agency, 2015, GNSS Market Report, accessed 11 July 2023, https://www.euspa.europa.eu/system/files/reports/GNSS-Market-Report-2015-issue4_0.pdf.

PwC, 2016, Copernicus: Market Report, accessed 11 July 2023, <https://www.pwc.com/jp/ja/industries/technology/tech-consulting/assets/pdf/copernicus-market-report.pdf>.

PwC, 2019, Copernicus Market Report, accessed 11 July 2023, https://www.copernicus.eu/sites/default/files/PwC_Copernicus_Market_Report_2019.pdf.

PwC, 2017, Interim Evaluation of Copernicus, accessed 11 July 2023, <https://www.copernicus.eu/sites/default/files/2020-05/ET0417742ENN.en.pdf>.

PwC, 2017, Copernicus ex-ante benefits assessment, accessed 11 July 2023, https://www.copernicus.eu/sites/default/files/2018-10/Copernicus-Ex-Ante-Final-Report_0_0.pdf.